

Spectrophotometric Study of Vanadium (IV) Complex with 4-Phenyl-7,8-dihydroxycoumarin (4-phenyl daphnetin)

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4-Phenyldaphnetin has already been used for the estimation of various metal ions. The present work deals with the spectrophotometric investigation of vanadium (IV)-4-phenyl daphnetin complex. The complex shows maximum absorption at 600 nm. The metal ion is completely complexed in the pH range 5.0-7.0. The complex has the molar composition of 1 : 2 and obeys Beer's law upto 3.6 ppm of vanadium. Tolerance limits of various interfering ions have been reported.

Sommer¹ investigated numerous hydroxy compounds and concluded that those possessing ortho- or peri- dihydroxy groups in an aromatic system are useful chromogenic reagents for several metal ions. Recently, orthodihydroxy coumarins and their substituted derivatives, have been employed for the spectrophotometric and gravimetric determination of niobium and tantalum².

The present investigation relates to the use of 4-phenyldaphnetin for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(IV). An acetone solution of the reagent produces a green coloured complex with aqueous solution of vanadyl ions. Vanadium(V) gives a similar colour reaction showing that it is reduced to vanadium(IV) by the ligand.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Unicam, SP 600, spectrophotometer, with 10 mm fused glass cells, was employed for absorption studies. Metrohm pH meter, model E-350, was employed for pH measurements.

*Preparation of 4-phenyldaphnetin*³: To a cold solution of pyrogallol in benzoyl acetic ester requisite amount of concentrated sulphuric acid was gradually added with stirring, keeping the temperature at 0°. The deep red viscous product thus obtained was kept in refrigerator for about 24 hrs. and then poured with stirring into water. The solid that precipitated was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was crystallised from benzene as colourless needles (m.p. 190°-92°). A standard solution of the ligand in acetone was used for the studies.

Standard V(IV) solution: 0.1M stock solution of vanadyl sulphate was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of vanadyl sulphate (pro analysi, E. Merck) in double distilled water and was standardised volumetrically. Solutions of requisite strength ($5 \times 10^{-5}M$) were obtained from the stock solution by dilution with water.

Absorption spectrum and effect of pH : In order to study the effect of pH on the absorbance of the complex, a series of solutions containing fixed amount of metal (1 ml of $5 \times 10^{-4}M$) and excess of ligand (1 ml of $2.5 \times 10^{-1}M$) were prepared at different pH values. The pH 's of the solutions were adjusted with dilute HCl and NaOH in a total volume of 10 ml, maintaining acetone concentration at 50% (v/v). The absorption spectra were recorded against the corresponding reagent blanks prepared under identical conditions. Some of the spectra are shown in Fig. 1, from which it is observed that the complex shows maximum absorbance at 600 nm. The nature of the spectra being similar, it is concluded that only one complex is formed in the system under these conditions. The absorbance of the complex rises as the pH is raised and it becomes maximum and then remains practically constant in the pH range 5.0–7.0. Above pH 7.0, the ligand exhibits considerable fluorescence. Further studies have been carried out at pH 6.2 and the wavelength 600 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of V(IV)-4-Phenyldaphnetin complex.

Metal Concentration = $5 \times 10^{-5}M$.

Reagent Concentration = $2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$.

Effect of time : The effect of time was studied by measuring the absorbance of a solution prepared at the pH 6.2 at regular intervals. The concentrations of metal and ligand in the solution were $5 \times 10^{-5}M$ and $2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ respectively. It has been found that maximum colour develops after 25 mins. It remains stable for ~ 6 hrs. after which absorbance begins to decrease slowly.

Effect of Buffers : Since pH was adjusted at 6.2 during most of the work, the effect of buffers was studied. It has been found that sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer is suitable for the purpose. The way pH is adjusted has no effect on absorbance. Whether pH is lowered or raised, absorbance at a particular pH remains the same.

Effect of acetone concentration : The effect of acetone concentration on the absorbance of the complex has been investigated. It has been found that change in concentration of acetone has no effect on the absorbance. However, 50% (v/v) concentration of acetone was maintained to keep the complex and ligand in solution.

Effect of reagent concentration : In order to study the effect of reagent on the absorbance of the complex, a series of solutions containing fixed amount of metal (1 ml of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$) and varying amounts of ligand were prepared. The pH was adjusted at 6.2 in a total volume 10 ml. The absorbance was measured against the corresponding reagent blank at 600 nm. The plot of absorbance vs. reagent concentration (Fig. 2) shows that the colour becomes practically constant when ~ 400 times molar excess of the ligand is present.

Fig. 2. Effect of reagent concentration on V(IV)-4-Phenyl daphnetin complex.

Physico-chemical constants of the complex : In order to study the linearity between the absorbance and the concentration of the metal ion, a series of solutions containing fixed amount of reagent and varying amounts of metal ions were prepared at pH 6.2 in 50% (v/v) acetone medium. The absorbances were measured against the corresponding reagent blanks. Linearity between absorbance and metal ion concentration was observed upto 3.6 ppm of vanadium. The sensitivity of the colour reaction as calculated from the Beer's law plot is $0.0055 \mu g V(IV)/cm^2$ for $\log I_0/I$ 0.001. The molar extinction coefficient for the complex comes out to be 8800.

Molar composition of the complex : Since the complex formed by vanadium(IV) with the ligand is weak, Job's method could not be employed for the determination of molar composition.

The molar composition was, however, determined by Asmus⁴ and Bent and French⁵ methods. In the Asmus method, increasing amounts of the chelating agent were added to a fixed amount of metal ion and absorbance measured. Plots of $1/A$ vs $1/V^n$, where V is the volume of ligand solution and $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, are shown in Fig. 3. It is seen that a straight line is obtained only when n is taken to be equal to 2, which gives the molar composition of complex.

Fig. 3. Composition of V(IV)-4-Phenyl daphnetin complex by grade method (Asmus).

For the Bent and French method also, the above data was used. A plot $\log [MR_n]/[M]$ vs. $\log [R]$ gave a straight line (Fig. 4) with the slope nearly equal to 2. This confirms that the metal : ligand ratio in the complex is 1 : 2.

Structure of the complex : Based upon the fact that the VO^{2+} ion generally forms five-coordinate complexes of tetragonal pyramid type⁶ and the molar composition of the complex comes out to be 1 : 2, a tentative structure for the complex may be written as :

Recommended Procedure for determination of vanadium : To a solution containing upto 36 μg of vanadium (IV or V), 2 ml of 5% 4-phenyldaphnetin solution in acetone is added. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 5.0-7.0, with sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid or acetate buffer and the volume is made up to 10 ml maintaining the acetone concentration at 50% (v/v). The absorbance is measured at 600 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. The amount of vanadium is then deduced from the calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions was studied by adding to the vanadium solution various cations and anions in appropriate amounts. The ligand was taken in large excess and pH was raised to 6.2. It was found that large number of anions do not interfere but cations interfere seriously.

Fig. 4. Composition of V(IV)-4-Phenyl daphnetin complex by Bent and French method.

The tolerance limits in ppm (in brackets) for various cations and anions with 2.5 ppm of vanadium were found to be : Titanium (5), molybdenum (9.5), nickel (23), magnesium (200), strontium (100), zinc (32), fluoride (560), tartrate (340), citrate (600), phosphate (180), borate (50), nitrate (60), thiosulphate (20), nitrite (400), chloride (4000), iodide (660), bromide (400), sulphite (80), thiocyanate (400).

DISCUSSION

The well known methods for the determination of vanadium are based on the use of phosphotungstic acid, hydrogen peroxide, 8-hydroxyquinoline (CHCl_3 extraction), formaldoxime and catechol. Their sensitivities are 0.02, 0.18, 0.016, 0.009 and 0.0009 respectively. The sensitivity in the case of 4-phenyldaphnetin is 0.0055, which is greater than those of the reagents listed above. Several anions do not interfere in this method even if present in very large amounts. In the determination of vanadium, titanium and molybdenum interfere in most of the other methods. Employing 4-phenyldaphnetin, vanadium can be determined in presence of comparable amounts of these metals.

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